

DRYAD

**Demonstration and modelling of
Nature-based solutions to enhance the
resilience of Mediterranean agro-silvo-
pastoral ecosystems and landscapes**

www.dryad-project.eu

Funded by
the European Union

The project

DRYAD supports the EU **Mission on Adaptation to Climate Change** by testing and developing **climate-resilient Nature-based Solutions (NBS) for Mediterranean agrosilvopastoral ecosystems (MAE) across Europe**. DRYAD combines scientific, technological, agricultural and social innovations to develop transformative solutions. It will be centered around **developing, modelling and demonstrating NBS** in 5 Mediterranean demonstration regions in collaboration with relevant actors and stakeholders. The results and knowledge sharing will then be scaled and transferred to 3 replicating regions.

DRYAD will develop **Decision Support System** for adaptive management and governance of climate adaptation solutions in MAE. DRYAD will engage **regional and local authorities, local stakeholders and landowners, research entities, private/public bodies, companies & citizens**, using co-creation, co-implementation, or co-validation processes within **Living Labs**. The project will provide tools and implementation guidelines to promote sustainable and climate-resilient transferable practices and facilitate regional adaptation plans, contributing to the **EU Nature Restoration Law and EU Mission on Adaptation to Climate Change**.

Methodology

The selection process of NBS and their testing and future implementation in the different regions requires significant time, as well as the involvement of multiple stakeholders, including government agencies. Thus, the project duration will be 48 months, **starting in September 2024 and ending in August 2028**. It is structured in **7 interrelated Work Packages**, 5 technical work packages (1, 2, 3, 4 and 5) will be related to the 2 transversal ones (6 and 7).

Objectives

With the long-term view of helping MEAs adapt to the impacts of climate change and improve their resilience, DRYAD Project aims to test **real-time, climate-resilient nature-based solutions for MAE**. These solutions will be developed, tested and demonstrated cooperatively with all the relevant actors in 5 different demonstration regions.

Specific Objectives (SOs)

SO1: Prioritizing and testing novel scientific tools and models to enhance the resilience of the Mediterranean agroforestry sector.

SO2: Demonstrating methodologies and management approaches in Pilot Demonstration Areas (PDA) focussing on increasing of MAE resilience to climate change and on mitigating multi-risk conditions by implementing NBS with the support of a Living Lab (LL) approach.

SO3: Demonstrating solutions by scaling PDA methodologies and management approaches into Demonstration Regions (DRs).
The most promising NBS will be transferred to 3 Replication Regions (RRs).

SO4: Improving reliability and dissemination of scientific methodologies and management approaches related to hydrological, biophysical and socio-economic aspects to face multi-risk conditions by bridging existing high Technology Readiness Level (TRL) modelling components into the Living Lab.

SO6: Improving stakeholder awareness on the opportunity and effectiveness of NBSs, through a set of tools and processes oriented to enhance resilience toward multiple ecological and socio-economic risks linked to climate change.

SO5: Co-creating and mutual learning processes at the local level, replicable, through a Community of Practice (CoP).

SO7: Supporting regions and local authorities in defining and developing a multilevel governance framework to tackle multi-dimensional, multi-level, and inter-sectoral policies.

DRYAD at a glance

The project is built upon the strategic lines of the Mediterranean basin regions. To begin this process, NBS will be tested in **5 demonstration regions**, using front-line scientific, technological, social, and business innovations as well as transformative solutions. Then, **the most promising NBS will be transferred to 3 replicating regions**. DRYAD will also develop Decision Support System to support multi-level and cross-sectoral integrated and adaptive governance.

Partners

This project is coordinated by the University of A Coruña (UDC). DRYAD includes **27 partners** from **6 different countries** (Spain, Netherlands, Portugal, Italy, Greece, France):

7 Universities

UNIVERSITY
OF TWENTE.

UNIVERSIDAD D CORDOBA

UNISS
UNIVERSITÀ
DEGLI STUDI
DI SASSARI

INSTITUTO
SUPERIOR D
AGRONOMIA
Universidade de Lisboa

1 National Laboratory

4 Public institutions

REGIONE AUTONOMA
DI SARDEGNA
REGIONE AUTONOMA
DELLA SARDEGNA

Junta de Andalucía
Consejería de Agricultura, Ganadería,
Pesca y Desarrollo Sostenible

6 Non – governmental / non-profit organizations / NGO

fundación
empresa
universidad
gallega

Centro Euro-Mediterraneo
sul Cambiamento Climatico

FONDAZIONE ETS

REPARTICIÓN NACIONAL
DE INVESTIGACIÓN CIENTÍFICA

Junta de
Castilla y León

FEDEHESA

FORESTS
FOR ALL
FOREVER
Forest Stewardship Council®

1 Research Centre

Consiglio Nazionale
delle Ricerche

3 Companies

ICATALIST

AGROOF

Companhia das Lezírias

2 Research Institutes

Instituto de Investigación y Formación Agraria
Pesquera, Alimentaria y de la Producción Ecológica
Consejo de Agricultura,
Pesca y Desarrollo Rural

3 Farmer organizations

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